

A DIGITAL-LEARNING PEDAGOGY FOR DEVELOPING ENGLISH LANGUAGE COMPETENCE IN PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This study explores the effectiveness of digital pedagogy in developing pre-service English teachers' language competence. A 14-week quasi-experimental study involved 64 participants divided into experimental and control groups. The experimental group used an LMS with forums, video conferencing, collaborative tasks, and feedback tools, while the control group received traditional instruction. Results showed higher improvement in language competence and professional communication among the experimental group. The findings confirm that digital pedagogy effectively supports teacher education.*

Keywords: *digital pedagogy; language competence; pre-service teachers; communicative competence.*

ЦИФРОВАЯ ПЕДАГОГИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА У БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ

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Аннотация. *Данное исследование изучает эффективность цифровой педагогики в развитии языковой компетентности будущих учителей английского языка. В 14-недельном исследовании участвовали 64 студента, разделённые на экспериментальную и контрольную группы. Экспериментальная группа обучалась с использованием LMS, форумов, видеоконференций и совместных заданий, а контрольная группа – традиционным способом. Результаты показали более высокий рост языковой компетентности в экспериментальной группе.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая педагогика; языковая компетентность; будущие учителя; коммуникативная компетенция.*

BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILARDA INGLIZ TILI KOMPETENSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH UCHUN RAQAMLI TA'LIM PEDAGOGIKASI

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***Annotatsiya.** Mazkur tadqiqot bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarining til kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda raqamli pedagogikaning samaradorligini o'rganadi. 14 haftalik tadqiqotda 64 nafar talaba eksperimental va nazorat guruhlariga bo'lindi. Eksperimental guruh LMS, forumlar, videokonferensiyalar va hamkorlikdagi topshiriqlar orqali ta'lim oldi, nazorat guruhi esa an'anaviy usulda o'qitildi. Natijalar eksperimental guruhda til kompetensiyasi yuqoriroq oshganini ko'rsatdi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** raqamli pedagogika; til kompetensiyasi; bo'lajak o'qituvchilar; kommunikativ kompetensiya.*

Introduction. Nowadays, the question of English language competence development in future teachers has arisen as one of the crucial issues related to contemporary teacher education. In the majority of countries, including Uzbekistan, besides being one of the subjects of study, English is considered to be necessary in communication, knowledge acquisition, and professional development. Therefore, one expects future teachers to speak and write in English efficiently and effectively while delivering lessons, explaining material, interacting, and communicating professionally. However, there exist some difficulties for teacher education programs to move students from mere theoretical knowledge about the English language to its actual communicative proficiency. The reason for this is that the curriculum for English lessons consists of theoretical parts, grammar tasks, and memorizing of rules, and students' actual communicative skills cannot develop enough because of lack of practice, collaboration, and feedback. According to recent researches, modern technologies can positively affect the learning process, learner autonomy, motivation, and overall language skills (Chapelle, 2001; Dudeney et al., 2014). Digital environment offers opportunities for constant communication, collaboration, and interaction with material. Nevertheless, further studies need to be conducted on the issue of using

technologies to support pre-service teachers' professional language competence. This study aims at exploring the efficiency of digital education in terms of improving the English language skills of pre-service teachers. Communicative tasks, collaboration, feedback, and reflective practice are the key aspects of digital pedagogy investigated within the framework of the study. **Methods** The methodology adopted in this study implies conducting a quasi-experimental research using a pre-test/post-test design in one semester (14 weeks). There were 64 third-year English pre-service teachers taking part in the research and dividing into experimental (32 people) and control (32 people) groups. In case of the control group, the participants were taught according to traditional principles involving textbooks, explanations, and exercises completed in class. Meanwhile, the experimental group received instructions via a digitally structured environment based on an online Learning Management System (LMS) consisting of:

- Discussion forums for asynchronous communication;
- Video conferencing for practice in speaking;
- Collaborative documents for group work;
- Recording software for oral assignments;
- Automated quizzes.

The instruments applied in the research included:

- Standardized English language proficiency test (pre-test and post-test);
- Rubric assessing fluency, clarity of explanations, pronunciation, and instructional communication skills;
- Rubric assessing grammatical correctness, organization, and effectiveness of writing;
- Perception survey;
- Activity log.

Quantitative data were analyzed descriptively and statistically (paired sample t-tests and independent sample t-tests), and qualitative data were analyzed thematically.

Results As a result of the research, significant differences were found in favor of the experimental group.

Table 1. Overall Language Competence Scores

Group	Pre-test Mean	Post-test Mean	Mean Gain
Experimental	62.1	84.3	22.2
Control	61.7	70.4	8.7

The improvement in the experimental group was over twice better than that of the control group. This difference was proven to be statistically significant ($p < .001$).

Table 2. Oral Performance Scores

Group	Pre-test	Post-test	Gain
Experimental	11.2	18.1	6.9
Control	11.0	13.8	2.8

Fluency, clarity of explanations, and confidence in speaking were noticeably higher in participants of the experimental group.

Table 3. Scores for Written Communication

Group	Pre-test	Post-test	Gain
Experimental	12.3	18.5	6.2
Control	12.5	14.7	2.2

The platform usage log demonstrated high participation rate in the digital environment – completion of 94% of all tasks. High levels of engagement correlated with more significant improvements.

Discussion It can be concluded from the obtained results that a digitally structured learning environment can be very efficient in developing language competencies in pre-service teachers. The results of this study proved that the

experimental group had greater gains than the control group in terms of overall language skills, oral communication abilities, and written professional communication. The obtained results correspond to previous findings related to efficiency of technology-enhanced learning since it is known that technology makes the process more engaging, provides autonomy, and involves much communicative practice. At the same time, reasons for such results may be numerous. For instance, participants in the experimental group had more opportunities to speak and use English actively; there were opportunities for immediate feedback; learners could have more flexibility in using materials. The current study proves that technology alone does not make an intervention successful; it should be integrated into clear pedagogical practices. Consequently, there are grounds to state that digital pedagogy can contribute to developing professional skills in future teachers. Further studies are recommended to explore potential effects during teaching practice and other universities.

Conclusion This study demonstrated that a digitally structured learning environment can significantly enhance the English language competence of pre-service teachers. Compared with traditional instruction, students who learned through digital tools achieved higher gains in overall proficiency, speaking performance, and written communication. The findings suggest that meaningful integration of technology, collaborative tasks, continuous feedback, and flexible learning opportunities can effectively support language development. Therefore, teacher education institutions should consider adopting well-designed digital pedagogy to better prepare future teachers for professional communication in English. Further research may examine long-term outcomes and application in different educational contexts.

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